

THE INTERPERSONAL IMPACT OF GENDER STEREOTYPES AND WAYS TO CORRECT THEM THROUGH PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING

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Abstract. This study, based on theoretical psychological analyses, presents data on the interpersonal relationships of gender stereotypes and methods for correcting gender stereotypes through psychological training. Based on these theoretical data, it is possible to eliminate various psychological problematic processes arising from the gradual implementation of the processes of organizing psychological trainings that help a person understand himself and assess the state of spiritual growth.

Keywords: Gender stereotypes, psychological research, psychological training, socio-spiritual relationships, worldview formation, cognitive states, psychological theories.

GENDER STEREOTIPLARINING SHAXSLARARO TA'SIRI VA ULARNI PSIXOLOGIK TRENING ORQALI KORREKSIYALASH USULLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda nazariy psixologik tahlillarga asoslangan holda gender stereotiplarining shaxslararo munosabatlarini o'rganish va psixologik treninglar orqali gender stereotiplarini korreksiyalash usullari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Bu nazariy ma'lumotlarga asoslangan holda insonning o'zini anglashga, ma'naviy yuksalish holatlarini baholashga yordam beruvchi psixologik treninglarni tashkil qilish jarayonlari bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshirish orqali kelib chiqqan har turli psixologik muammoli jarayonlarni bartaraf etish mumkin bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Gender stereotiplari, psixologik tadqiqotlar, psixologik treninglar, ijtimoiy-ma'naviy munosabatlar, dunyoqarashni shakllantirish, kognitiv holatlar, psixologik nazariyalar.

Introduction

Nowadays, the issues of interpersonal gender stereotypes that exist in modern society are an integral part of the social life of a person, individual psychological development and the formation of his worldview, and are a system dependent on spiritual and cultural values. In the field of psychology, the concept of gender stereotypes directly affects the level of thinking and reasoning of a person, socio-spiritual relationships, choice of profession, fulfillment of family roles, and even self-esteem. Therefore, the issue of understanding gender stereotypes through psychological training and based on research that monitors their occurrence, getting rid of them, and establishing equality is one of the current areas of psychology.

Gender stereotypes have been formed in society for many years and serve to define the strict boundaries of the roles of "male" and "female" in a broad sense. Through these stereotypes, men are given such characteristics as strength, determination, leadership, independence, and women are given such characteristics as kindness, obedience, passivity, and family responsibility.

If, based on such a psychological approach, a person's internal capabilities are limited, this negatively affects the process of self-expression. Gender stereotypes are manifested in connection with the strengthening of certain social roles in the family, professional, and other spheres.

Usually, women are assigned family roles such as mother, housewife, and spouse as their main tasks, while men are assigned professional roles. In modern society, men are often evaluated based on their professional achievements, and women are evaluated based on their family and children. Psychological training can create opportunities for determining the socio-psychological adaptation of a person, improving communication skills, and activating the process of self-awareness. Psychological training methods are recognized as an effective tool, especially in eliminating or reassessing gender stereotypes.

The term "gender" refers to social and cultural roles, in contrast to a biological person. A person acquires a system of behavior, values, and morals that are considered appropriate for his or her personality from birth in society. Thus, we analyze the idea that gender is a social construct formed by society based on the methods that determine the role of a person as "male" or "female".

Gender stereotypes are a system of ideas that are reflected in society, but are not always correct, ensuring the stability of the behavior of men and women. These stereotypes limit the individual's opportunities for self-development, create psychological barriers to the individual's self-expression in spiritual maturity, and lead to a state of socio-spiritual inequality. From a psychological point of view, it should be noted that gender stereotypes are reinforced by such psychological mechanisms as "socially determined situations" and "cognitive situations".

The negative impact of gender stereotypes can be observed mainly within the family: strict socio-spiritual protection requirements applied to gender roles impose on women only tasks that arise in the family, such as raising children and housework, and do not allow them to demonstrate their professional potential. The greatest danger of the negative impact of gender stereotypes on various aspects of social life is the emergence of gender stereotypes based on them. In psychology, the concept of gender stereotypes is not a natural process, but a process based on socio-cultural constructions. They are formed under the influence of the following main factors: Based on family upbringing - from an early age, a child begins to assimilate gender roles through the behavior of his parents, their words, and relationships.

Simply put, the education system - based on the approaches of teachers, the distribution of roles in subject textbooks - also forms gender stereotypes. It is also reinforced through the media - through advertising, films, images on social networks, and roles that are considered typical for men and women. Cultural values and national traditions - manifested in some societies where patriarchal systems prevail and male supremacy has become the norm. In cases based on religious and ideological views - in some cases, religious interpretations can also be an obstacle to gender equality. From a psychological point of view, these stereotypes lead to the following consequences: Internal conflicts - when people try to use their abilities in activities that are not

gender-specific, they encounter internal contradictions. As a result, gender stereotypes prevent a person from fully realizing their creative and intellectual potential.

Psychological trainings mainly help to conduct active educational and psychological processes aimed at self-awareness, developing communication skills and broadening their worldview, re-evaluating stereotypes. The main goal of psychological training is used in the following cases - to form a conscious attitude towards gender stereotypes in people, to teach them to freely express their opinions, and to establish equality in interpersonal relationships through corrective methods. The main psychological methods used in the training process: Role-playing - empathy is formed by alternating male and female roles; Discussion and reflection - participants analyze their experiences; Psychodrama - overcoming internal barriers by posing gender conflicts; Cognitive reappraisal - a technique for analyzing and changing stereotyped thoughts; Through training exercises - positive changes can be made through cooperation, communication, and the study of socio-spiritual roles. In applied psychology, psychological training programs aimed at reducing gender stereotypes are successfully used in the education system, corporate teams, and family psychology.

Conclusion

The results of the study show that after the training, the following changes were observed in the participants: The level of gender stereotypes decreased; Emotional empathy increased; Self-confidence increased; The level of social adaptation improved. Gender stereotypes are formed in society, but in many cases they are outdated and restrictive social norms. They prevent the free development of the individual and his full self-expression. Therefore, the mitigation or elimination of such stereotypes through psychological training is an important direction of modern psychological practice.

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